

Laser induced graphene papers enabled functional composites for liquid monitoring

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Abstract

Fiber-reinforced polymeric composites (FRP) had a wide range of applications in aerospace industry. During their service process, FRP would undergo various harsh air conditions, such as strong sunlight, storm wind and acid rain. Acid rain corrosion is the most common natural phenomenon. Due to various influence factors such as rainfall frequency, temperature and acid rain medium, the corrosion process was complicated and unpredicted. It was difficult to real-time monitor the corrosion location and degree of the FRP by traditional mechanical testing methods. In this paper, LIGP liquid sensors was used for detecting the presence of organic solvents. Compared to traditional liquid sensors, LIGP exhibits higher response sensitivity and has the unique and special sensing mechanism. LIGP liquid sensor array is also applied to monitor the location of composite which is threatened by liquids. With the key findings, the sensors have great potential in monitoring organic solvent leakages of pipelines and fabrication of smart anti-corrosion composite structure. At last, we highly anticipate that the LIGP liquid sensor array could protect composites from hazard liquids and acid rain, and monitor the degree of erosion of composites.

Figure1

Figure2

Conclusion

A flexible and portable LIGP-based liquid sensor with fast response and good reproducibility is reported. LIGP shows its advantages of lightweight, simple preparation, low cost, roll-to-roll production and environmental protection. Then, the possible sensing mechanism is proposed from the view-point of processing-structure-property relationship. Morphologies of LIGP determined barriers of charge carriers and their migration distance and resulted in different sensitivity. Based on the sensing results, LIGP sensor array is applicable to monitor the location of composites exposed to harmful liquids and predict the degree of erosion by organic solvents. The multifunctional LIGP liquid sensor with the scalable processing technique demonstrated in this work can be highly valuable in organic solvents transportation and smart composites preparation for developing self-monitoring solvents pipelines and smart anti-corrosion composites structures.